

**OF CHILDREN THROUGH THE ART OF MUSIC SPIRITUAL,
AESTHETIC AND MORAL TASTE QUALITIES EXPLAIN THE
CONTENT AND FIND**

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Anntation. This article discusses the development of children's music rolan spiritual and aesthetic qualities in taste and npr, as well as being close to a person in brine is of the beauty and the spiritual world.

Keywords: aesthetic taste, aesthetic education, beauty, refinement, perfection by npr music, culture, education, generation of mature, feelings and thinking.

Comprehensive children mature, nurturing, spiritual and aesthetic of the perfect human of very great importance to be given special attention to the education process. The role of education in solving this issue is larger spiritual and aesthetic of music. Become much wider spiritual and aesthetic education, and society teaches a holistic perspective to the perception of beauty in the person. Also, spiritual and aesthetic activities, beauty rules the realities on the basis of the person capable to change trains. Spiritual and aesthetic development of the mind of the person, and perfection, to last long, which is the birth of relations and business process. Moral - aesthetic education of man is one of the factors which plays an important role in the spiritual fullness, someone's wishes, not because of

the opportunity that arises from the legitimate needs of society is necessary. Moral - aesthetic attention to education do not appear to be either yesterday or today. Its roots go back far into the past. Ancient Egypt, China, India, Greece, philosopher, a man of serious attention to the issues of spiritual and physical perfection Rumi is. He Nevai, thinkers like Rumi in the teachings of spiritual maturity, as a most important condition was noted. In today's period, too, in the human being, a beautiful, zooming into the spiritual realm of education is the main objective. Because the spiritual and aesthetic education is relevant to all areas of our social life.

Currently developing, advancing and in which each person in the society who have the moral high - time to achieve the aesthetic taste is required. Because the only true free thinking spiritual and aesthetic taste of the owner of the potential to the world, the country will have the ability to see through the beauty of the life form." Moral - aesthetic education of the task to teach not only beautiful and assessment to understand the addition of social life to encourage you to participate in the implementation. Moral - the problem of aesthetic education, are within the framework of public opinion from the beginning. Too many thoughts on this in recent times, he said. Some spiritual - aesthetic creatively active people bringing up issues of education in the main function, the interaction xunuklik to teach the difference from say other provisions beautiful, high spirituality while others again, bringing up says advanced aesthetic tastes are noted. Moral - aesthetic aesthetic taste of one of the main functions of education is education. Aesthetic aesthetic tastes a specific role in the system of consciousness is the most sensitive, controversial, interesting and topical issues, as well as the difficult one. One of the specific features during its realities, aesthetic, things to see events or issued in the case is manifested in the price. See for the first time the works of art, made to the book mutuala mushtariy age, profession, education level, according to will give you a different price. These aspects of its own, which

is typical of a particular person only, however, it is important for a society that shows that this is not a personal issue. This is simply “I like or do not like” words expressed by elections, although our tastes, our aesthetic, our outlook, cultural-tim I will show you. At this price our look, our experience, the society we live in, the period is also reflected in the views of a certain sense.

The unity of spiritual and aesthetic tastes, emotions and thought, human self-gini, representing him at the same time also, the price given is not even him. The period we lived in aesthetic taste, our eyes open country, we heard the song, we are interested in read books, newspapers, magazines such as the perception of spiritual riches and formed in the process of developing. Everyone has their own citizens of the state, as a citizen even of their time. If you can be out of those circles with herself living habits and ethics, then their activities, you can choose your tastes and needs. The man of the surrounding environment occurs through spiritual and aesthetic taste. Man dwells in the world of beautiful things and the parts, ideological, and aesthetic aspects of artistic works is in communication with the press and mature, learn from beautiful to enjoy content, you will feel it, creates it. Instead, tubal tubanlashtirib also puts the taste of the human environment. Although the aesthetic taste with spiritual and artistic taste are different from each other, always with each other to fill will go. Spiritual artistic taste and aesthetic taste is based on samples of different artistic genres of literature, including the story, narrate, and classical works in them the realities artistic fine tool journal-khan shows the influence of emotions, and helps the development of the perception of artistic values, spiritual and aesthetic pleasure. High moral in society - many of those who have a sense of his ministry aesthetic, cultural, ethical and aesthetic aspects in the development and plays an important role.

Likely to contribute themselves to the art of world music of great composers of adding Betxoven l. v., v. a. Motsart, i. s. and other composers

created music of a different person depending on your mood and situation affect Article identified. Tunes composed in the spirit of humanitarian kindness and yet they also listen to muhlis to be loved by you. Even with the difference of living umidbaxsh some excellent tunes and were in medicine, and in medical institutions qo'llanayotgan concerns also worthy of note is the fact that they give good results. Music is spiritual and aesthetic education society conducted complete the image of the person to become a huge component of balanced should work in a nurturing way. A stand out among the masses propaganda musical, full-blown, the results will not be achieved. Children activities with music, especially plays a major role. Music evoke strong emotional feelings in the human soul. Music perception with the help of his artistic growth, will go further enrich and emotions. Growing perception in the age of music dedicated to their love of music is enough interest to stand, comprehensive physical, spiritual and moral qualities of nurturing will not be rich. The mood music is a huge source of spiritual and aesthetic. The impact this man during his whole life feeling, evoke emotions, hayajonlantirib was called to action. Music man inspired to'lqinlantirib his heart, the tetiklashtirib strength was dedicated. Mungli the same time I sing and play the man's grief-g'ussa to distress throws. The extent of this man in many ways to the perception of music, and the ability to listen to her adopters, aesthetic tastes, depending on the general culture.

Since ancient times, man listen I own playing musical instruments in the song of the birds or the sound of resonance-imaging, the flow of water that came today hashorotlar to reflect the move. According to people's thinking and the art of music to express emotions is served. Thinking music to influence emotions and those side-is the perception of emotional and restore it to the surrounding realities and will help you to change. His statement to those emotions emotional expression in music which reflect, to contemplate, showing the effects of mindset, it is directed towards a certain goal, side-hayrixohlik around and wake your

attitude changes. Music through the art of children's spiritual, moral qualities and explain the content of various types of musical activity find aesthetic taste, in particular, we have the performer, the song say, musical-an action, rhythm, vocal performance, game-inssenirovka, music instruments, and music education is necessary to ensure participate in the creation of the music. Every type of the music business, such as children's knowledge expands the range of additional knowledge will help you to master. The level of quality to the music (the most common emosiya draw from, creativity appeared before), adolescents, individual predisposition, will power and mental ability will depend on. In this place, hear and most importantly emotional components. Intonatsiya age of singing, musical character than pyesa was trained under different emotional effects. The game to know them at the same time, differentiate between opposite and analogy to similar parts, sound, rhythm, dynamic teach you to know the relations, music, the ability to sing, to feel the rhythm and performer as well as skills have grown.

Moral - aesthetic education of the individual in society is related music culture to take hold, and different ways of using a form is carried out. Music in the life of the emotions to himself, not feeling exactly, they selected a random moment from peeled, anglangan is from the perspective of certain dreams. The most complicated feelings of it thus takes the most sensitive and also the expression of mood. Music to follow the criteria of time, thus they stand for change, and avjlanishi will cover the process of decline. The music complex social emotions, above all, reflect the tone of speech or action concerning corrugated in life, the moral emotions, thus, love, hatred, pride, fear, aesthetic art or the elegance of nature, the glory, tragic, funny feelings represents. The power of music is, when it is to rejoice, to care, imaginations, push bardamlik, depression and similar mental state in the mutual connection private and in a general way, it represents a way to soak each other. Uzbek national music classical music of the pearl of the status of the game, we are the people of

uzbekistan and complex history, experiences, pleasure and ecstasy, the grief-complaints of dreams and hope so thoughtful, deep, elegant, attractive, passionate of expression, as if he heard it goes into the world of sweet imaginations.

The conditions that promote the idea of dirt in the current conflict of the period of national mental perfect the human spirit contrary to the idea of spiritual and aesthetic education of children in the event will not remain without effect. After all, the identities of persons, find, above all, which is based on the formation of moral and ethical qualities. So the culture of the individual with society, their mutual independence explain the strengthening of the spiritual affiliated dialektik to find a resolution that is an important condition.

In this regard it is noteworthy that we may say, the art of music the old traditions of the culture of the people of the east after progressing the development of the form, the subscriber has its place in music culture and the world we recognized that that may be necessary.

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